

NFDI4Objects
Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

Interdisciplinary Knowledge Graphs Semantic Modelling using Linked Open Data, Wikibase and the Wikiverse

Staatliche Museen zu Berlin
Preußischer Kulturbesitz

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CHNT29 | 2024 | 04-06 Nov 2024 | Vienna | Austria | 06/11/24

Session: Research Data Management in Cultural Heritage goes Digital

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via trentu.ca

Roland Soré, via flickr [rolibin/30105173063](https://www.flickr.com/photos/rolibin/30105173063/)

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

archaeological_site	megalith
historic	archaeological_site
historic:civilization	neolithic
name	Crvena stijena
name:en	Red wall
wikidata	Q121418883
wikipedia	https://bs.wikipedia.org/wiki/Crvena_stijena_(Crna_Gora)

Fig. 14.9. Examples of cutmarks observed on specimens taxa other than ungulates at Crvena Stijena: a) mammoth mandible (M5); b) hare distal tibia (M1); c) *Ursus* sp. metapodial fragment (XXIV); d) *Ursus* sp. fifth metacarpal fragment (M1).

via researchgate [320957331](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320957331) The Paleolithic Faunal Remains from Crvena Stijena

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Xalaros, Attribution, via Wikimedia Commons

Research data in archaeology is interdisciplinary, heterogeneous, and must always be considered in a domain-related context

In order to make this data interchangeable, a common understanding and community-driven standardised implementation are required

F A I R

FINDABLE

ACCESSIBLE

INTEROPERABLE

REUSABLE

Dr. Heidi Seibold, CC BY 4.0, via 10.5281/zenodo.8070860

via <https://5stardata.info/> and <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

FAIR graphs are created with Linked Open Data ...

2007

2008

2009

2010

2011

2017

2018

2019

2020

2023

Florian Thiery, based on lod-cloud.net, CC BY 4.0, via [Wikimedia Commons](https://commons.wikimedia.org/)

... resulting in the **Linked Open Data Cloud**.

❖ Items

Label
Description
Alias
Identifier

❖ Statements

Property
Value
Qualifier
Reference

Mtrognitz, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

Wikibase & Wikidata Datamodel

Wikibases in the Wikibase Ecosystem and wikibase.cloud

Wikibases integrated into the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

HOWEVER - How can we reach this huge Knowledge Graph?

In NFDI4Objects we implemented it like this ...

The following slides will show some LOD / Wikibase examples

Ogham Stones

How to create Linked Open Ogham Stones?

R.A.S. Macalister, *Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum*, vol. I (1945) / p.502

4.-6. AD early Medieval “Primitive Irish”

Al-qamar / CC BY-SA 3.0 via Wikimedia Commons

Florian Thiery, CC BY-SA 4.0

Ogham!

Florian Thiery, Timo Homburg, Sophie C. Schmidt und Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

The open Ogham data workflow!

CIIC 81

- UCC Cork Stone Corridor: #4
- OSM Node: 11071361392
- Wikidata: Q130529871

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

↑ Florian Thieri, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Knoten: CIIC 81 /
UCC 4 (11071361392)

Version #2

added metadata

Bearbeitet vor 19 Tagen von fthiergeo

Änderungssatz #139090380

Standort: 51.8938126, -8.4921198

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
inscription	C[A]SSITT[A7O]S MAQI MU[CO]I CALLITI
moved	yes
moved_to	Q69379477
name	CIIC 81 / UCC 4
project	ogham.link
source	survey
wikidata	Q106680733

↑ Florian Thieri, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Use each LOD/ Wikibase-Instance for data it is “famous” for

- *Linked Open Ogham Data*: providing the primary URI
 - <https://t1p.de/3xqti>
- *fuzzy-sl Wikibase*: coordinates and how they are created
 - [P4](#)
- *Wikidata*: data-hub for external identifiers, e.g., OSM, SMRS, LOD
 - [P11693](#), [P4057](#), [P2888](#)
- *Semantic Kompakkt Wikibase*: 3D Model & Annotations
 - [P74](#), [P75](#)
- *FactGrid Wikibase for Historians*: Inscription & Persons & Words
 - [P1219](#), [P33](#), [P256](#)

The Idea: Create LOD and feed domain-specific Wikibase Instances

via <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25505959>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL; <https://www.openstreetmap.org/relation/6168494>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL;
<https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/562702954>

alt_name	Garranes Ringfort
archaeological_site	fortification
fortification_type	ringfort
historic	archaeological_site
historic:civilization	celtic
name	Lisnacaheragh Ringfort

Rath called Lisheenagreine
ca. 51.81655, -8.76587

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Past: CIIC 81 at the original? findspot in Garranes (Lisheenagreine)

Florian Thier, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Today: Looking at the UCC Stone corridor

[Main page](#)
[Recent changes](#)
[Random page](#)
[Help about MediaWiki](#)

Tools

[What links here](#)
[Related changes](#)
[Special pages](#)
[Printable version](#)
[Permanent link](#)
[Page information](#)
[Concept URI](#)

Wikibase

[New Item](#)
[New Property](#)
[New Schema](#)
[All Properties](#)
[Query Service](#)
[Cradle](#)
[QuickStatements](#)

In other languages

[Add links](#)

Item [Discussion](#)

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q74)

Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork	

Statements

instance of	<div>Archaeological Site</div> <div>▼ 0 references</div>
related to	<div>http://wikidata.org/entity/Q130529871</div> <div>related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch</div> <div>▼ 0 references</div>
related to	<div>https://wikibase.semantic-kompakt.de/entity/Q1247</div> <div>related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch</div> <div>▼ 0 references</div>
related to	<div>https://database.factgrid.de/entity/Q1000294</div> <div>related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch</div> <div>▼ 0 references</div>
related to	<div>http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081</div> <div>related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch</div> <div>▼ 0 references</div>

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q74>

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

fuzzy-sl Wikibase [Q74]

51°48'59.58"N, 8°45'57.13"W

certainty level Low

certainty description Gippert/Web, Ogham 81:
 According to Brash, JRSAI 10, 1869, 260, the stone was found in a structure called Rath Lisheenagreine, in the townland of Gurranes (sic!), parish of Templemartin, 1 mle. north of the parish church (the village in question is named "Gurranes" in the Cork U.C. too). A detailed map of the rath (in connection with the larger Rath Lisnacaheeragh) is available in S.P. O' R'Yordain's article in PRIA 47-C, 1941-42, 77 ff. - According to Brash, the stone was discovered by one farmer Crowley 17 years before (the publication of his article in JRSAI 10, 1869); Macalister states in CIIC that it "has been known since the sixties" and "appears to have come from a souterrain in the group" of "earth-works" on the townland of Gurranes. The first report was made by John Lyons, C.C., Newcestown, Enniskeane; Brash's visit took place on 16.12.1868. The stone was moved to the Museum of the U.C., Cork after Macalister first visited it (at that time it was still "standing loosely in one of the ditches": CIIC 1, 84). In the collection of the U.C., it is assigned no. 17.!

method used Georeferencing

acting person Florian Thiery

source type (generic) Textual Description

source type (detail) Paper

method description found in old documents

precision ±0.0001°

location type Findspot

point type Location of a Place as a Concept

has coordinate

51°53'37.3"N, 8°29'32.6"W

certainty level High

certainty description on-site survey at exhibition area

method used on-site survey

acting person Florian Thiery

source type (detail) on-site survey (source type)

source type (generic) on-site survey (source type)

method description on-site survey at UCC Cork

precision ±0.0001°

location type Exhibition Site

point type Exhibition

0 references

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q74>

fuzzy-sl Wikibase [Q74]

- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new item
- Recent changes
- Random item
- Query Service
- Nearby
- Help
- Donate

- Lexicographical data
- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes
- Random Lexeme

- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI
- Cite this page
- Get shortened URL
- Download QR code

Item [Discussion](#)

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q130529871)

Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor
CIIC 81

edit

▼ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor	CIIC 81
German	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	
Bavarian	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	ogham stone edit	+ add reference
	▼ 0 references	
	Ogham Stone Semantic Concept edit	+ add reference
	▼ 0 references	
	archaeological artifact edit	+ add reference
	▼ 0 references	
		+ add value

Identifiers

FactGrid item ID Q1000294

▼ 0 references

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID CO074-148----

▼ 0 references

OpenStreetMap node ID 11071361392

▼ 0 references

Wikidata [Q130529871]

- Main page
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help about MediaWiki

- Wikibase
- New item
- New property
- New schema
- List properties
- Query service

Tools

- What links here
- Related changes
- Upload file
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI

In other languages

[Add links](#)

Item [Discussion](#)

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q1247)

3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor [edit](#)

[In more languages](#)

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor	
British English	No label defined	No description defined	

[Mapping to other ontologies](#)

Predicate	URL
+ add mapping	

Statements

instance of [Media item](#) [edit](#)

[0 references](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

license [Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike](#) [edit](#)

[0 references](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

has technique [Photogrammetry](#) [edit](#)

file view

<https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb>

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV

3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

Related agents

Rightsowner: [University College Cork \(UCC\)](#)

Data Creator: [Anne-Karoline Distel](#)

Creator: [Anne-Karoline Distel](#)

Editor: [Florian Thiery](#)

Contact Person: [Florian Thiery](#)

Licence

[Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International \(CC BY-NC-SA 4.0\)](#)

Creation

Technique: [Photogrammetry](#)

Software: [KIRI engine](#)

Equipment: Smartphone

Date: Invalid Date

Related object structure

[Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV](#)

cassittas (Q1013406)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	cassittas	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

CnFdI
3D DATA ENRICHMENT

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Wikibase
New item

Item Discussion

C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81) (Q1255)

Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81)	Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI

Semantic Kompakkt [Q1247]

- Main page
- Query service
- Sample queries
- Advanced text search
- Recent changes

- Browse
- FactGrid Viewer
- KnolBase Browser
- EntiTree genealogies

- Project Spaces
- Blog
- Projects historically
- Projects alphabetically
- Projects personally
- To Do
- SPARQL Lab

- Items & Properties
- New Item
- MergeItems
- Batch fragments
- QuickStatements
- Directory of Properties
- New Property
- Data modeling
- Help

- Lexemes
- New Lexeme
- Search

- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI

Item [Discussion](#)

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q1000294)

Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

▼ In more languages

Language	Label	Description
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor
British English	No label defined	No description defined

Statements

Instance of [Ogham Stone](#) ▼ 0 references

Research projects that contributed to this data set [The FactGrid Ogham Project \(2024-\)](#) ▼ 0 references

Language [Ogham](#) ▼ 0 references

Genre classification [Ogham Stone](#) ▼ 0 references

Script style [Ogham](#) ▼ 0 references

inscription [C\[A\]SSITT\[A\]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI](#) ▼ 0 references

Persons mentioned [cassittas](#) ▼ 0 references

[Calliti](#) ▼ 0 references

Things mentioned [MAQI](#) ▼ 0 references

[MUCOI](#) ▼ 0 references

cassittas (Q1013406)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	cassittas	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

Calliti (Q1013407)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Ston

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	Calliti	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Ston

MAQI (Q1013408)

son
 MAQ | MAC | /-ᚱ- | MACCI | MAQQI | MACV | MACI

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	MAQI	son	MAQ MAC /-ᚱ- MACCI MAQQI MACV MACI

MUCOI (Q1013410)

túath, tribe
 /-ᚱ- | MACCU | MOCU | MOCOI | MOCO

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	MUCOI	túath, tribe	/-ᚱ- MACCU MOCU MOCOI MOCO

FactGrid [Q1000294]

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelper Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: NFDI4Objects Graph --> ?item ?geo [GeoSPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource

Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name: oghamsite

```

Valid Query
1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

GeoConcepts (23)

- AnnotatedThing
- Barony
- Barony
- County
- County
- Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
- GeographicLocation
- Island
- Kiln region (KinRegion)
- Location
- Location (Location)
- OghamSite
- Place
- ProductionCentre
- Province
- State
- Townland
- Townland
- geosparql:Feature
- sf:MultiPolygon
- sf:Point
- sf:Polygon
- wgs84_pos:SpatialThing

<https://t1p.de/v0lg7>

Squirrel Data | Linked Open Ogham | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network

Linked Ogham

81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)^{EN}

<http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081>

The 81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search: Go Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL) Download

Description: comment:Ogham Stone, Ireland

Property	Value
disclosedAt (oghamonto:disclosedAt)	OS40000120 (fslid:OS40000120)
exactMatch (oghamonto:exactMatch)	Q106680733 (wde:Q106680733) [x]
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OghamStone (oghamonto:OghamStone) [x] OghamStone_Squirrel (oghamonto:OghamStone_Squirrel) [x] Resource (ldp:Resource) [x] Resource (Resource) [x]
comment (rdfs:comment)	Ogham Stone, Ireland (rdflangString) (iso639:en)
label (rdfs:label)	81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (rdflangString) (iso639:en)

Metadata

Property	Value
identifier (dce:identifier)	81 (xsd:string)
creator (terms:creator)	0000-0002-3246-3531 (0000-0002-3246-3531) [x]
license (terms:license)	deed.de (deed.de) [x]
rightsHolder (terms:rightsHolder)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0000-0002-3246-3531 (0000-0002-3246-3531) [x] 0000-0003-4696-2101 (0000-0003-4696-2101) [x]
inDataset (void:inDataset)	Linked_Open_Ogham (fslid:Linked_Open_Ogham) [2481 oghamonto:disclosedAt]
wasAttributedTo (prov:wasAttributedTo)	PythonStonesCIIC (fslid:PythonStonesCIIC)
wasDerivedFrom (prov:wasDerivedFrom)	og_stones.csv (og_stones.csv) [x]
wasGeneratedBy (prov:wasGeneratedBy)	Y50000081_activity (fslid:Y50000081_activity)

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NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

SPARQL endpoint /api/sparql (see documentation)

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

Table Response 196 results

item	label	geo	county	count
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000031>	'Ballyknock (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-8.071111 52.026944)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Cork'@en	'15'"@xsd:integer
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000002>	'Drumlohan (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-7.468056 52.163056)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Waterford'@en	'10'"@xsd:integer
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000020>	'Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-10.031111 52.1725)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Kerry'@en	'9'"@xsd:integer
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000149>	'Kilcolaght East / Kilhullicaha (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-9.747222 52.071944)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Kerry'@en	'8'"@xsd:integer
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000170>	'Knockboy (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-7.6 52.111389)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Waterford'@en	'8'"@xsd:integer
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000019>	'Ballinrannig (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-10.386111 52.176111)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Kerry'@en	'7'"@xsd:integer
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000077>	'Coolmagort (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-9.642778 52.061111)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Kerry'@en	'7'"@xsd:integer
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000073>	'Colbinstown / Killeen Cormac (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-6.756389 53.031111)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Kildare'@en	'7'"@xsd:integer
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000030>	'Ballyhank (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-8.608333 51.838611)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Cork'@en	'6'"@xsd:integer
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000173>	'Knockshanawee (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-8.794722 51.868056)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Cork'@en	'6'"@xsd:integer
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000230>	'Whitefield (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-9.703056 52.080556)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Kerry'@en	'5'"@xsd:integer
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000154>	'Kilgrovan (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-7.549722 52.090556)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Waterford'@en	'5'"@xsd:integer
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000185>	'Monataggart (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-8.779444 51.974444)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Cork'@en	'4'"@xsd:integer
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000208>	'Rockfield / Laharan (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-9.631667 52.128889)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Kerry'@en	'4'"@xsd:integer
<http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000209>	'Rooves More (Ogham Site)'@en	'POINT(-8.784167 51.886667)'"@geo:wktLiteral	'Cork'@en	'3'"@xsd:integer

LOD Resource as "hub-concept" for the N4O Knowledge Graph ...

- Antrim
- Armagh
- Carlow
- Cavan
- Clare
- Cork
- Donegal
- Dublin
- Fermanagh
- Galway
- Kerry
- Kildare
- Kilkenny
- Leitrim
- Limerick
- Londonderry
- Louth
- Mayo
- Meath
- Roscommon
- Tipperary
- Tyrone
- Waterford
- Wexford
- Wicklow

- 1 - 2
- 2 - 3
- 3 - 4
- 4 - 5
- 5 - 6
- 6 - 7
- 7 - 8
- 8 - 9
- 9 - 10
- 10 - 11
- 11 - 12
- 12 - 13
- 13 - 14
- 14 - 15

... to query it e.g. using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin.

Wikibase / Query Service Examples

Query Helper Filter

+ Show

object of representation file view wikidata id

Limit

[Query source](#)

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wdqs: <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql>
4
5 SELECT DISTINCT ?CIIC81Label ?3D_view ?wd_id ?OSM_id ?SMRS_id ?LOD_id ?Factgrid_id WHERE {
6   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
7   VALUES ?CIIC81 {tib:Q1407}
8   ?Media_item tib:P63 ?CIIC81.
9   ?Media_item tib:P74 ?3D_view.
10  ?CIIC81 tib:P107 ?wd_id.
11
12  BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(wd:), ?wd_id)) AS ?wd_item)
13
14  SERVICE wdqs: {
15    ?wd_item wdt:P11693 ?OSM_id;
16            wdt:P4057 ?SMRS_id;
17            wdt:P2888 ?LOD_id;
18            wdt:P8168 ?Factgrid_id.
19  }
20 }
21

```

1 result in 513 ms

CIIC81Label	3D_view	wd_id	OSM_id	SMRS_id	LOD_id	Factgrid_id
Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb	Q130529871	11071361392	CO074-148----	http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081	Q1000294

Federating between Semantic Kompakkt & Wikidata

Federating between Wikidata (external IDs), FactGrid (related people and inscriptions), and fuzzy-sl (coordinates)

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
4 PREFIX fslwd: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/entity/>
5 PREFIX fslwdt: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/prop/direct/>
6 PREFIX fg: <https://database.factgrid.de/entity/>
7 PREFIX fgt: <https://database.factgrid.de/prop/direct/>
8
9 SELECT ?label ?wikiq ?factgridq ?fslq ?inscription ?related_personsLabels ?coordinates ?osmnode ?smrid ?uri WHERE {
10 SERVICE <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql> {
11   ?wikiq wdt:P31 wd:Q2016147.
12   FILTER(?wikiq = wd:Q130529871)
13   ?wikiq rdfs:label ?label.
14   FILTER(LANG(?label) IN("en"))
15   ?wikiq wdt:P8168 ?factgridq;
16     wdt:P11693 ?osmnode;
17     wdt:P4057 ?smrid;
18     wdt:P2888 ?uri.
19 }
20 SERVICE <https://database.factgrid.de/sparql> {
21   fg:Q1000294 fgt:P1219 ?inscription;
22   fgt:P33 ?related_persons;
23   fgt:P1215 ?fslq.
24   ?related_persons rdfs:label ?related_personsLabels.
25   FILTER(LANG(?related_personsLabels) IN("en"))
26 }
27 SERVICE <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/query/sparql> { fslwd:Q74 fslwdt:P4 ?coordinates. }
28 }

```

<https://sparql.dblp.org/YKlrP3>

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Query results:

2 lines found 11ms in total 11ms for computation 0.0ms for resolving and sending

	?label	?wikiq	?factgridq	?fslq	?inscription	?related_personsLabels	?coordinates	?osmnode	?smrid	?uri
1	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Q130529871	Q1000294	Q74	C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI	cassittas	Point(-8.492443111 51.893659305)	11071361392	CO074-148---	Y50000081
2	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Q130529871	Q1000294	Q74	C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUCOI CALLITI	Calliti	Point(-8.492443111 51.893659305)	11071361392	CO074-148---	Y50000081

Citizen Science

How to work within Wikidata?

via <https://w.wiki/AQ2F>

via https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_HolyWells

Wikidata:WikiProject HolyWells

Wikidata Entry: WikiProject HolyWells (Q1294424); supported by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network (Q12019170)

1 Holy Wells in Ireland

1.1 Statements to model a holy well in Ireland

1.2 Examples

1.3 SPARQL created List

1.4 SPARQL List as Map / Image Map

1.5 Contributions

Holy Wells in Ireland ^[edit]

Statements to model a holy well in Ireland ^[edit]

Use English and Irish labels in the header, where known.

Property	Example	Explanation
instance of (P11)	Holy Well Semantic Concept (Q12944332)	always use this. Define it as a holy well, no matter whether there is still veneration happening or not.
holy well (Q1217047)	holy well (Q1217047)	
instance of (P11)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> state of use (P5817): "in use" for holy wells where veneration is still happening or "abandoned", where that is the case state of conservation (P5110): preserved (Q5557619) / in danger (Q5555585) / demolished or destroyed (Q5555515) 	
instance of (P11)	religious site (Q10503324)	only where veneration is still happening, i.e. annual pilgrims or people regularly visiting the well for private prayers or to relieve the holy water
instance of (P11)	water source (Q1217046)	only where there is actually still water at the site, helps to filter out dried up wells / springs
country (P17)	Republic of Ireland (Q27)	no
located in the administrative territorial entity (P131)	County Kilkenny (Q18023) • Ballin (Q5551337)	County = civil parish
diocese (P126)	Roman Catholic Diocese of Ossory (Q123907)	Roman Catholic diocese in which the holy well is located
coordinate location (P128)	coordinate location derived from OpenStreetMap or Historic Environment Viewer	add reference URL (P129) or stated in (P248)
street address (P127)	use, when the only location given is a field name or similar	
described by source (P134)	O'Kelly, The Place-Names of County Kilkenny (Q12617451) Historic Environment Viewer (Inland) (Q12000194) The Schools' Collection (Q12393246) Canon W. Carignan: The History and Antiquities of the Diocese of Ossory (Q1244544) with its volumes	add page(s) (P124) or reference URL (P129)
image (P18)		image
video (P15)		
Commons category (P127)	Category:Toberishole, Cattan_2	
named after (P138)	Beig of Kilkenny (Q50076) eye (Q7294)	saint representing patron saint or body part representing cure for ailment
open days (P122)		pattern days, if it is still celebrated
Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID (P4087)	KX006-133-___	plus reference URL (P129)
OpenStreetMap node ID (P11865)	6153432366	OpenStreetMap Node ID or way ID
Wiki Loves Monuments ID (P138)	IE-KX-0327	Wiki Loves Monuments ID (optional for accessible ones)

via <https://w.wiki/AQ2F>

The Citizen Science Wikidata Project Holy Wells

b-unicycling, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oWvIB>

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

Example Freshford: St Lachtain's Well in Wikidata

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/935503837>

Toberlachtain (Q121840779)

Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kilkenny

Language Label Description Also known as

English	Toberlachtain	Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kilkenny	Tober Lachtain St. Lachtain's Well Toberlachtain
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

Instance of

- holy well (1 reference)
- Holy Well Semantic Concept (0 references)
- spring (3 references)
- holy well (state of use: abandoned, date: 1839) (1 reference)

Image

Toberlachtain Tober Lachtain 02.jpg (3,008 × 2,000, 3.54 MB)

named after

- Lachtain mac Tairin (0 references)

country

- Ireland (0 references)

located in the administrative territorial entity

- County Kilkenny (0 references)
- Freshford (0 references)

diocese

- Roman Catholic Diocese of Ossory (0 references)

coordinate location

Freshford

52°43'53.76"N, 7°23'22.24"W (1 reference)

collection

- Pádraig Ó Dálaigh: The holy wells of County Kilkenny II (0 references)

inventory number

- 137 (collection: Pádraig Ó Dálaigh: The holy wells of County Kilkenny II) (0 references)

medical condition treated

- blindness (1 reference)
- eye infection (1 reference)

external data available at URL

- <https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/freshford-st-lachtain-well-low-poly-ae1e114d4a704332bbf76407134e81e> (copyright license: Creative Commons Attribution) (0 references)

described by source

- O'Kelly: The Place-Names of County Kilkenny (page(s): 13) (0 references)
- Historic Environment Viewer (Ireland) (1 reference)
- The Schools' Collection (2 references)
- Letters containing information relative to the antiquities of the county of Kilkenny collected during the progress of the Ordnance Survey in 1839 (written, source, paragraph, or column: vol. I, par. 188; vol. I, p. XXXI) (0 references)
- The History and Antiquities of the Diocese of Ossory II (page(s): 256) (0 references)

described by source

- 6 Inch First Edition Ordnance Survey map of Ireland (0 references)
- Pádraig Ó Dálaigh: The holy wells of County Kilkenny in terms of documentary coverage, location, ritual practice and oronomastic concept, vol. I (page(s): 90) (0 references)
- Pádraig Ó Dálaigh: The holy wells of County Kilkenny II (page(s): 137) (0 references)
- Nooks and Corners of County Kilkenny by Paris Anderson (page(s): 61) (0 references)
- Eleanor Cantwell: Threecastles (page(s): 33-34) (0 references)
- Historical, Social and Pictorial Sketches of Freshford (page(s): 48) (0 references)
- Red Book of Ossory (0 references)

Commons category

- Toberlachtain (0 references)

Identifiers

- Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID: KK013-025- (1 reference)
- OpenStreetMap way ID: 935503837 (0 references)
- Wiki Loves Monuments ID: IE-KK-0248 (0 references)

OpenStreetMap

Suchen

Weg: Saint Lachtain's Well (935503837)

Version #7

added sketchfab link

Bearbeitet vor 3 Monaten von b-unicycling

Änderungssatz #152597977

Tags

alt_name	Toberlachtain
amenity	place_of_worship
check_date	2023-08-25
denomination	roman_catholic
description	Walled enclosure with wrought iron gate. Stone paved ground with subcircular water basin which is covered in water lenses.
name	Toberlachtain
name:en	Saint Lachtain's Well
name:en:wikidata	Q121840779
name:ga	Tober Lachtain
natural	spring
place_of_worship	holy_well
ref:Esamr	KK013-025
religion	christian
source	British War Office mapsurvey

Identifiers

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID

KK013-025----

1 reference

OpenStreetMap way ID

935503837

0 references

via <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121840779>

Example Freshford: St Lachtain's Well in Wikidata

Samian Research relational database

Linked Open Data based on CIDOC CRM

publication via archaeology.link

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryheifer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: Wikidata --> ?item ?geo [SPARQL Endpoint]

Quick Add RDF Resource

Filter Concept Results:

GeoConcepts (500) FeatureCollections GeometryC

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wikibase: <http://wikiba.se/ontology/#>
4 PREFIX p: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/>
5 PREFIX ps: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/statement/>
6 PREFIX pq: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/qualifier/>
7 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
8 PREFIX bd: <http://www.bigdata.com/rdf#>
9
10 #defaultView:Map{"hide":["?geo"]}
11 # Samian Ware Productioncentres
12 SELECT ?item ?samian ?itemLabel ?geo ?layer WHERE {
13   ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q102202026;
14   wdt:P361 wd:Q90412636;
15   wdt:P625 ?geo;
16   wdt:P2888 ?samian;
17   wdt:P706 ?layer.
18   ?layer wdt:P31 wd:Q102201947.
19   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
20 }

```

Gespeicherte Queries: ChristSch Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: English (en)

via <https://w.wiki/BA3A>

SPARQL Unicorn

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0. Data via Wikidata, CCO and Samian Research, m-DPPL

The Samian Research LOD / Wikidata Workflow

Wikidata Community, Public Domain, via w.wiki/6HLh


```
Wikidata Query Service
# Samian Ware Discovery Sites
#defaultView:Map
SELECT ?item ?samian ?itemLabel ?geom
WHERE
{
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q102202066.
  ?item wdt:P361 wd:Q90412636.
  ?item wdt:P625 ?geom.
  ?item wdt:P2888 ?samian.
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
```

Wikidata Community, Public Domain, via w.wiki/6HLm


```
Wikidata Query Service
# Samian Ware Productioncentres
#defaultView:Map
SELECT ?item ?samian ?itemLabel ?geom
WHERE
{
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q102202026.
  ?item wdt:P361 wd:Q90412636.
  ?item wdt:P625 ?geom.
  ?item wdt:P2888 ?samian.
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
```

Wikidata Community, Public Domain, via w.wiki/4pDu


```
Wikidata Query Service
# Samian Ware Kilnregions
#defaultView:Map["hide":["?geo","?samian"]]
SELECT ?item ?samian ?itemLabel ?geom ?layer WHERE {
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q102201947;
  wdt:P361 wd:Q90412636;
  wdt:P2888 ?samian;
  wdt:P3896 ?geom.
  optional { ?item wdt:P2888 ?layer. }
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
```


The Samian Research LOD / Wikidata Entities

Croton Numismatics

Hoard analyses of the silver coinage of Croton

Berlin, Staatliche Museen zu Berlin,
1873 Fox, 18257570, 7,78 g, 29 mm, 12 h

Hoard analyses of the silver coinage of Croton

Florian Thiery / Stefanie Baars, CC BY 4.0

A lot of findspots show uncertainties and vague information

There is only the information that **the hoard was found on the river Esaro, without specifying exactly where on the river course**. In the literature, there is information that it was found "in Crotona", by which the city rather than the province is meant, otherwise it would have been formulated differently. The urban area of the river course ends shortly after the "Strada Statale 106 Jonica". **The most likely location for the find is along the course of the river between the section just before the motorway and the mouth of the river in the sea**. Since the find was made in 1967, the course of the river at that time probably corresponds fairly closely to the course of the river today. However, both the latter and the presumed find section are conjectures.

Example: Find at Esaro River in 1967

via https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/croton-geo/site_3003/

Fiume Esaro 1967 (gennaio) EN

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/crotonsite_3003

The Fiume Esaro 1967 (gennaio) resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search: Go **Download Options:** Format: Turtle (TTL)

Description: comment:Am "Fiume Esaro".

Description: scopeNote:Am "Fiume Esaro".

Property	Value
<code>certaintyDesc</code> (fsl:certaintyDesc)	Es gibt lediglich die Information, dass der Hortfund am Fluss Esaro gefunden wurde, ohne genaue Angabe, wo am Flusslauf. In der Literatur gibt es die (...) Information, dass er "in Crotona" gefunden wurde, womit eher die Stadt als die Provinz gemeint sein dürfte, da es ansonsten anders formuliert worden wäre. Der städtische Bereich des Flusslaufes endet kurz hinter der "Strada Statale 106 Jonica". Am wahrscheinlichsten ist der Fundort am Flusslauf zwischen dem Abschnitt kurz vor der Autobahn und der Flussmündung im Meer. Da der Fund 1967 getätigt wurde, entspricht der damalige Flussverlauf vermutlich ziemlich genau dem heutigen. Sowohl Letzteres als auch der mutmaßliche Fundabschnitt sind jedoch Vermutungen. (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
<code>certaintyLevel</code> (fsl:certaintyLevel)	low (fsl:low) [x]
<code>dubiousMatch</code> (fsl:dubiousMatch)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 137318585 (osmw:137318585) [x] Q6681 (wikidata:Q6681) [x]
<code>hasReference</code> (fsl:hasReference)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> E. A. Arslan (2014) (xsd:string) P. Attianese (1980) (xsd:string)
<code>partOf</code> (fsl:partOf)	CrotonProject (fsl:CrotonProject) [x]
<code>siteType</code> (fsl:siteType)	ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
<code>spatialType</code> (fsl:spatialType)	River (fsl:River) [x]
<code>hasGeometry</code> (gsp:hasGeometry)	crotonsite_3003_geom (fsl:crotonsite_3003_geom)
<code>type</code> (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov:Entity) [x] Place (pleiades:Place) [x] Site (fsl:Site) [x]
<code>comment</code> (rdfs:comment)	Am "Fiume Esaro". (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
<code>label</code> (rdfs:label)	Fiume Esaro 1967 (gennaio) (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
<code>prefLabel</code> (skos:prefLabel)	Fiume Esaro 1967 (gennaio) (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
<code>scopeNote</code> (skos:scopeNote)	Am "Fiume Esaro". (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
<code>is member of</code> (rdfs:member of)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity Instances Collection (fsl:Entity_collection) Place Instances Collection (fsl:Place_collection) Site Instances Collection (fsl:Site_collection)
<code>is used</code> (prov:used of)	crotonsite_3003_activity (fsl:crotonsite_3003_activity)

Property	Value
<code>certaintyDesc</code> (fsl:certaintyDesc)	Es gibt lediglich die Information, dass der Hortfund am Fluss Esaro gefunden wurde, ohne genaue Angabe, wo am Flusslauf. In der Literatur gibt es die (...) Information, dass er "in Crotona" gefunden wurde, womit eher die Stadt als die Provinz gemeint sein dürfte, da es ansonsten anders formuliert worden wäre. Der städtische Bereich des Flusslaufes endet kurz hinter der "Strada Statale 106 Jonica". Am wahrscheinlichsten ist der Fundort am Flusslauf zwischen dem Abschnitt kurz vor der Autobahn und der Flussmündung im Meer. Da der Fund 1967 getätigt wurde, entspricht der damalige Flussverlauf vermutlich ziemlich genau dem heutigen. Sowohl Letzteres als auch der mutmaßliche Fundabschnitt sind jedoch Vermutungen. (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
<code>certaintyLevel</code> (fsl:certaintyLevel)	low (fsl:low) [x]
<code>dubiousMatch</code> (fsl:dubiousMatch)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 137318585 (osmw:137318585) [x] Q6681 (wikidata:Q6681) [x]
<code>hasReference</code> (fsl:hasReference)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> E. A. Arslan (2014) (xsd:string) P. Attianese (1980) (xsd:string)
<code>partOf</code> (fsl:partOf)	CrotonProject (fsl:CrotonProject) [x]
<code>siteType</code> (fsl:siteType)	ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
<code>spatialType</code> (fsl:spatialType)	River (fsl:River) [x]

Fiume Esaro 1967 (gennaio) als LOD

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q67>

- Main page
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help about MediaWiki

Tools

- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI

Wikibase

- New Item
- New Property
- New Schema
- All Properties
- Query Service
- Cradle
- QuickStatements

In other languages

[Add links](#)

Item [Discussion](#)

Fiume Esaro 1967 (gennaio) (Q67)

Am `Fiume Esaro`.

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Fiume Esaro 1967 (gennaio)	Am `Fiume Esaro`.	

Statements

instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Archaeological Site ▼ 0 references
has reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> P. Attianese (1980) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ 0 references E. A. Arslan (2014) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ 0 references
related to	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> http://openopenstreetmap.org/way/137318585 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#dubiousMatch ▼ 0 references http://wikidata.org/entity/Q6681 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#dubiousMatch ▼ 0 references

has coordinate

39°57.800′N, 17°6′44.280′E﻿ / ﻿

certainty level	Low
method used	Georeferencing
acting person	Stefanie Baars
source type (detail)	Paper
source type (generic)	Textual Description
method description	set a point based on P. Attianese (1980) and E. A. Arslan (2014) using OSM Way 137318585
certainty description (with language)	There is only the information that the hoard was found on the river Esaro, without specifying exactly where on the river course. In the literature, there is information that it was found "in Crotona", by which the city rather than the province is meant, otherwise it would have been formulated differently. The urban area of the river course ends shortly after the "Strada Statale 106 Jonica". The most likely location for the find is along the course of the river between the section just before the motorway and the mouth of the river in the sea. Since the find was made in 1967, the course of the river at that time probably corresponds fairly closely to the course of the river today. However, both the latter and the presumed find section are conjectures. (English)

There is only the information that the hoard was found on the river Esaro, without specifying exactly where on the river course. In the literature, there is information that it was found "in Crotona", by which the city rather than the province is meant, otherwise it would have been formulated differently. The urban area of the river course ends shortly after the "Strada Statale 106 Jonica". The most likely location for the find is along the course of the river between the section just before the motorway and the mouth of the river in the sea. Since the find was made in 1967, the course of the river at that time probably corresponds fairly closely to the course of the river today. However, both the latter and the presumed find section are conjectures. (English)

Es gibt lediglich die Information, dass der Hortfund am Fluss Esaro gefunden wurde, ohne genaue Angabe, wo am Flusslauf. In der Literatur gibt es die Information, dass er "in Crotona" gefunden wurde, womit eher die Stadt als die Provinz gemeint sein dürfte, da es ansonsten anders formuliert worden wäre. Der städtische Bereich des Flusslaufes endet kurz hinter der "Strada Statale 106 Jonica". Am wahrscheinlichsten ist der Fundort am Flusslauf zwischen dem Abschnitt kurz vor der Autobahn und der Flussmündung im Meer. Da der Fund 1967 getätigt wurde, entspricht der damalige Flussverlauf vermutlich ziemlich genau dem heutigen. Sowohl Letzteres als auch der mutmaßliche Fundabschnitt sind jedoch Vermutungen. (German)

point type	Representative Point
precision	±0.000001°
location type	Findspot

Fiume Esaro 1967 (gennaio) in the fuzzy-sl Wikibase

Campanian Ignimbrite

Findspots from the CI eruption 40,000 yr b2k

Breislak, Scipione (1748-1826). Voyages physiques et lythologiques dans la Campanie. Paris: Dentu, Imprimeur-libraire, 1801, via https://vulcan.lindahall.org/12_large.shtml

About 40,000 yr b2k ago, the largest eruption of the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) took place in the Phlegraean Fields.

Evidence of the ash fall from this late Pleistocene volcanic event can be found throughout Central Europe.

These sites are recorded in several publications, e.g. with coordinates or references to cities, regions, caves and archaeological sites.

via https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/Site_collection/index.html

Squirrel Data | CI FSL | *powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network* Nuts?

Site Instances Collection EN

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/Site_collection

The Site Instances Collection resource is powered by Static [GeoPubby](#) generated using the [SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin](#)

Search: Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL)

Property	Value
<code>type</code> (rdf:type)	<code>FeatureCollection</code> (gsp:FeatureCollection) [x]
<code>label</code> (rdfs:label)	Site Instances Collection (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
<code>member</code> (rdfs:member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▼ 71 values▪ Acerra Sink (fsl:csite_1)▪ Acqua Fidia (fsl:csite_2)▪ Balta Alba (Romania) (fsl:csite_57)▪ Batajnica (fsl:csite_104)▪ Bratul Borcea (Romania) (fsl:csite_56)▪ Capezzano (fsl:csite_3)▪ Casola (fsl:csite_4)▪ Castelcivita Cave (fsl:csite_5)▪ Copechia (fsl:csite_6)

All these sites and information can be published as Linked Open Data

Figure 1. Geographic distribution of the Campanian Ignimbrite deposits, including archaeological and sampling sites mentioned in the paper. Solid squares: CI tephra occurrences and related thickness in cm (in italics if reworked) [modified from *Cornell et al., 1983; Amirkhanov et al., 1993; Cini Castagnoli et al., 1995; Narcisi and Vezzoli, 1999; Fedele et al., 2002; Upton et al., 2002*]. Dotted area in central Italy: distribution of the CI-derived paleosol (CI-PS [Frezza and Narcisi, 1996]). Solid triangles: archaeological sites with CI ash layer. Blank triangles: archaeological sites with ash layer attributed to the CI on the basis of cultural-stratigraphic position and ^{14}C dating (Fedele et al., 2002; Giaccio and Isaia, on file). Solid circles: selected European Palaeolithic sites within the area potentially affected by the CI air-fall.

Franchthi Cave (Greece) in Fedele et al. (2003)

Zde, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Zde, CC BY-SA 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Xalaros, Attribution, via Wikimedia Commons

https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/cisite_45/index.html

Squirrel Data | CI FSL | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network

Franchthi Cave (Greece)
http://fuzzy-squirrel.link/data/cisite_45

The Franchthi Cave (Greece) resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search: Go Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL) Download

Description: comment:CI findspot related from literature
 Description: scopeNote:CI findspot related from literature

Property	Value
certaintyDesc (fsl:certaintyDesc)	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper and found on OpenStreetMap (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
certaintyLevel (fsl:certaintyLevel)	high (fsl:high) [x]
hasReference (fsl:hasReference)	Fedele et al., 2003 (xsd:string)
partOf (fsl:partOf)	CampanianIgnimbriteProject (fsl:CampanianIgnimbriteProject) [x]
siteType (fsl:siteType)	ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x]
spatialType (fsl:spatialType)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ArchaeologicalSite (fsl:ArchaeologicalSite) [x] Cave (fsl:Cave) [x] Site (fsl:Site) [x]
hasGeometry (gsp:hasGeometry)	cisite_45_geom (fsl:cisite_45_geom)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity (prov:Entity) [x] Place (skos:Place) [x] Site (fsl:Site) [x]
comment (rdfs:comment)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
label (rdfs:label)	Franchthi Cave (Greece) (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
closeMatch (skos:closeMatch)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1221172811 (1221172811) [x] Q1441331 (wikidata:Q1441331) [x]
prefLabel (skos:prefLabel)	Franchthi Cave (Greece) (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
scopeNote (skos:scopeNote)	CI findspot related from literature (rdf:langstring) (iso6391:en)
is member (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entity instances Collection (fsl:entity_collection) Place instances Collection (fsl:place_collection) Site instances Collection (fsl:site_collection)
is used (prov:used) of	cisite_45_activity (fsl:cisite_45_activity)

Franchthi Cave as Archaeological Site (fsl:cisite_45) in the LOD Cloud

Auel Maar (AU3/4) & Dehner Maar (DE3) sites in Schenk et al. (2024)

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q70>

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Tools
What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase
New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

Item Discussion

Auel Maar AU3 (Q70)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Auel Maar AU3	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of	Geological Site	0 references
related to	https://kulturdb.de/einobjekt.php?id=23391 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch	0 references
has reference	Schenk et al. (2024)	1 reference
part of	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots	0 references
has spatial type	Maar	0 references

has coordinate	50°16′57.0″N, 6°35′42.4″E
certainty level	High
certainty description	stated in scientific paper, Schenk et al. (2024), fig. 1
method used	Georeferencing
acting person	Fiona Schenk
method description	site survey
source type (detail)	Paper
source type (generic)	Textual Description
precision	±0.0001°
location type	Findspot
point type	Investigation Place
1 reference	
reference URL	https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017

via <https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017>, Fig. 1

Auel AU3 [Q70] in the fuzzy-sl Wikibase

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q84>

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Tools
What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase
New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

Item [Discussion](#)

Auel Maar AU4 (Q84)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Auel Maar AU4	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of Geological Site
▼ 0 references

related to <https://kulturdb.de/einobjekt.php?id=23391>
related to type <http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch>
▼ 0 references

has reference Schenk et al. (2024)
▶ 1 reference

part of Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots
▼ 0 references

has spatial type Maar
▼ 0 references

has coordinate 50°16′55.6″N, 6°35′41.6″E

certainty level	High
certainty description	stated in scientific paper, Schenk et al. (2024), fig. 1
method used	Georeferencing
acting person	Fiona Schenk
method description	site survey
source type (detail)	Paper
source type (generic)	Textual Description
precision	±0.0001°
location type	Findspot
point type	Investigation Place

▼ 1 reference

reference URL	https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017
---------------	---

via <https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017>, Fig. 1

Auel AU4 [Q84] in the fuzzy-sl Wikibase

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q85>

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Tools
What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase
New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

Item [Discussion](#)

DE3 Dehner Maar (Q85)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	DE3 Dehner Maar	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of	Geological Site	▼ 0 references
related to	https://kulturdb.de/einobjekt.php?id=8502 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch	▼ 0 references
has reference	Schenk et al. (2024)	▶ 1 reference
part of	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots	▼ 0 references
has spatial type	Maar	▼ 0 references

has coordinate	50°17′34.1″N, 6°30′23.8″E
certainty level	High
certainty description	stated in scientific paper, Schenk et al. (2024), fig. 1
method used	Georeferencing
acting person	Fiona Schenk
method description	site survey
source type (detail)	Paper
source type (generic)	Textual Description
precision	±0.0001°
location type	Findspot
point type	Investigation Place
▼ 1 reference	
reference URL	https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017

via <https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017>, Fig. 1

Auel DE3 [Q85] in the fuzzy-sl Wikibase

Provenance Research

How to create a “provenance gazetteer”?

- as “Meta-Index”
- as “common reference terminology”
- as “data hub”

Item Discussion

Dr. Philipp Lederer (Q25)

Coin Dealer in Berlin edit

In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Dr. Philipp Lederer	Coin Dealer in Berlin	
German	Dr. Philipp Lederer	Münzhändler in Berlin	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

- instance of
 - Concept
 - 0 references
 - + add reference
 - Person / Human
 - 0 references
 - + add reference
 - + add value
- in scheme
 - Person-Gazetteer
 - 0 references
 - + add reference
 - + add value
- has role
 - Coin Dealer
 - 0 references
 - + add reference
 - + add value

via <https://n4o-prov.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q25>

Münzkabinett Staatliche Museen zu Berlin Interaktiver Katalog des Münzkabinetts

START SUCH E KARTE

Antoniuss Pius
140-144 n. Chr.
Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen

Vorderseite ANTONINVS AVG PVS P P Draperte Panzertüste des Antonius Pius in der Rechtenansicht nach r.

Rückseite COS III / TR POT Antonius Pius führt mit Marcus Aurelius und Lucius Verus in einem Viergespann (quadriga) nach r.

Dargestellte/r Antonius Pius, Marcus Aurelius, Lucius Verus

Münzstand Antike Herrscherprägung

Münzher/r Antonius Pius

Datierung 140-143 n. Chr. Römische Kaiserzeit

Nominal Aureus 7,42 g, 20 mm, 6 h

Herstellung geprägt

Münzstätte Rom

Region Italia

Land Italien

Bild Dateien sind lizenziert als Public Domain Mark 1.0. Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen, 18273152, Aufnahme durch Bernhard Wessier.

Münzkabinett Staatliche Museen zu Berlin Interaktiver Katalog des Münzkabinetts

START SUCH E KARTE

Vorschau für gespartes Objekt

Popollonia
3. Jh. v. Chr.
Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen

Münzstand Staat

Datierung 3. Jh. v. Chr. Hellenismus

Nominal Quadrans 1,52 g, 27 mm, 3 h

Münzstätte Popollonia

Region Etruria

Land Italien

Schlaggriff Münze

Abteilung Antike, Griechen, Hellenismus

Accession 1936/137

Zugangsjahr 1936

Fundort Italien

Objektnummer 18269072

Permalink <https://ikmk.smb.museum/object?id=18269072>

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Münzkabinett Staatliche Museen zu Berlin Interaktiver Katalog des Münzkabinetts

START SUCH E KARTE

Alexandria: Marcus Aurelius
187/168 n. Chr.
Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen

Vorderseite M AVPAOC ANTONINO C E E rund, Omega (vierseitig), Kopf des Marcus Aurelius mit Lorbeerkranz nach r.

Rückseite L H (im Abschnitt, durch Stempelbruch schwer lesbar), Darstellung einer Göttermahnt (Hermes mit Vorn nach r. auf einer Lage mit drei Nischen, Sarapis, Harpokrates, Isis, Demeter, Hermes), Über jeder Gottheit je ein rechteckiger Raum mit knienden Figuren, in festschließender Komposition, mittig Tyche?

Dargestellte/r Marcus Aurelius

Münzstand Antike Herrscherprägung

Münzher/r Marcus Aurelius

Datierung 187/168 n. Chr. Römische Kaiserzeit

Nominal Bronze 24,51 g, 37 mm, 12 n

Herstellung geprägt

Münzstätte Alexandria

Region Ägypten

Land Ägypten

Bild Dateien sind lizenziert als Public Domain Mark 1.0. Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen, 18273178, Aufnahme durch Bernhard Wessier.

Münzkabinett Staatliche Museen zu Berlin Interaktiver Katalog des Münzkabinetts

START SUCH E KARTE

Vorschau für gespartes Objekt

Tarsos
ca. 222-235 n. Chr.
Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen

Münzstand Staat

Datierung ca. 222-235 n. Chr. Römische Kaiserzeit

Münzstätte Tarsos

Region Kilikien

Land Türkei

Webportale <https://rpc.ashmus.ox.ac.uk/coins/70782>

Schlaggriff Münze

Abteilung Antike, Griechen, Römische Kaiserzeit

Accession 1933/412

Zugangsjahr 1933

Objektnummer 18311140

Permalink <https://ikmk.smb.museum/object?id=18311140>

Bild Dateien sind lizenziert als Public Domain Mark 1.0. Berlin, Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen, 18311140, Aufnahme durch Bernhard Wessier.

images via <https://ikmk.smb.museum/object?id=18273152>, <https://ikmk.smb.museum/object?id=18267378>, <https://ikmk.smb.museum/object?id=18269072>, <https://ikmk.smb.museum/object?id=18311140>

Wikibase instances as Terminology Hubs

Person ND

Name Lederer, Dr. Philipp (25.08.1872 - 02.09.1944)

Coin dealer in Berlin.

Numismatist and coin dealer from 1911 (or 1910?), previously from 1898 employed by J. Hirsch in Munich. Lederer wrote his Phd on the coinage of Segesta in 1910.

National service from September 1915, served as private in the Baltics. Return to Berlin in early 1919. Lederer's office was opposite the Kaiser-Friedrich-Museum (now Bode-Museum) at the Kupfergraben.

H. A. Cahn's obituary stresses Lederer's good relationship with the Berlin Museums even after 1933. Lederer was forced to emigrate to Switzerland following the events of November 1938.

Lit.: K. Priebe, Berliner Münzhandel, BBPN 21, 2013, pp. 252; Obituary, BNZ 1950/51, pp. 148-149; H. A. Cahn, Obituary, SNR 32, 1946, pp. 69-73; J. Schwartz, Scheinbare Sicherheit - Geschäftsbeziehungen Philipp Lederers und seine NS-Verfolgungsgeschichte in: J. Schwartz - S. Voigt (eds.), Spuren der NS-Verfolgung. Provenienzforschung in den kulturhistorischen Sammlungen der Stadt Hannover (2019) pp. 137-159, esp. 138-139, 142, 145.

Types Design ND, Vendor (to Museum) ND, Vendor (to prev. Owner) ND

GND <https://d-nb.info/gnd/143778765> ID

Wikipedia [de] https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Philipp_Lederer W

VIAF <https://viaf.org/viaf/103209084> VIAF

<https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/term/BIOG59166> i

Wikidata <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q2086982> W

Permalink <https://ikmk.smb.museum/ndp/person/4077>

via <https://ikmk.smb.museum/ndp/person/4077>

- Main page
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help about Wikibase
- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI
- Wikibase
- New Item
- New Property
- New Schema
- All Properties
- Query Service
- Cradle
- QuickStatements
- In other languages
- [Add links](#)

Item Discussion

Dr. Philipp Lederer (Q25)

Coin Dealer in Berlin

In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Dr. Philipp Lederer	Coin Dealer in Berlin	

All entered languages

Statements

- instance of Concept

0 references
- Person / Human

0 references
- in scheme Person-Gazetteer

0 references
- has role Coin Dealer

0 references

via <https://n40-prov.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q25>

Create unique PIDs for persons / corporate bodies ...

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Tools
What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase
New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

Item [Discussion](#)

Dr. Philipp Lederer (Q25)

Coin Dealer in Berlin

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Dr. Philipp Lederer	Coin Dealer in Berlin	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concept <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ 0 references Person / Human <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ 0 references
in scheme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Person-Gazetteer <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ 0 references
has role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coin Dealer <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ 0 references

aligned with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://ikmk.smb.museum/ndp/person/4077 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> alignment type: exact match alignment repository: NDP ▼ 0 references
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://d-nb.info/gnd/143778765 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> alignment type: exact match alignment repository: GND ▶ 1 reference
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> http://viaf.org/viaf/103209084 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> alignment type: exact match alignment repository: VIAF ▶ 1 reference
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> http://wikidata.org/entity/Q2086982 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> alignment type: exact match alignment repository: Wikidata ▶ 1 reference
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Philipp_Lederer <ul style="list-style-type: none"> alignment type: exact match alignment repository: Wikipedia ▶ 1 reference
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/term/BIOG59166 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> alignment type: exact match alignment repository: British Museum ▶ 1 reference

via <https://n40-prov.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q25>

.. link them to other resources in the WWW ..

Conclusion

Linked Open Data to query
interdisciplinary Knowledge Graphs

If we store and publish our data as Linked Open Data ...

via <https://5stardata.info/> and <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

... we are able to query a huge knowledge graph ...

The screenshot shows the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin interface. The main window has a menu bar with 'Linked Data Processing', 'Queryhelfer', 'Einstellungen', and 'Hilfe'. Below the menu bar are tabs for 'Abfragen', 'Interlinken', and 'Anreicherung (Experimentell)'. The 'Endpoint auswählen:' dropdown is set to 'NFDI4Objects Graph --> ?item ?geo [GeoSPARQL Endpoint]'. The 'Queryvorlagen:' dropdown is set to '10 Random Geometries'. The 'Layer Name:' field is empty. The 'Valid Query' section contains the following SPARQL query:

```
1 SELECT ?item ?geo WHERE {  
2 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <> .  
3 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .  
4 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .  
5 } LIMIT 10
```

The 'Filter Concept Results:' field is empty. The 'GeoConcepts (23)' list shows the following items:

- AnnotatedThing
- Barony
- Barony
- County
- County
- Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
- GeographicLocation
- Island
- Kiln region (KilnRegion)
- Location
- Location (Location)
- OghamSite
- Place
- ProductionCentre
- Province
- State
- Townland
- Townland
- geosparql:Feature
- sf:MultiPolygon
- sf:Point
- sf:Polygon
- wgs84_pos:SpatialThing

The bottom of the window has a 'Gespeicherte Queries:' dropdown, 'Query laden' and 'Query speichern' buttons, a 'Queryname:' field, and a 'Layer hinzufügen' button. The 'Language for query results:' dropdown is set to 'English (en)'.

The screenshot shows the 'ClassTree (426)' panel. The top tabs are 'GeometryCollections' and 'ClassTree (426)'. The list of classes is as follows:

- taxonomy
- terminology
- thesaurus
- wgs84_pos:SpatialThing
- Annotation
- Barony
- Barony
- County
- County
- OghamSite
- OghamStone
- OghamStone_CIIC
- OghamStone_CISP
- OghamStone_O3D
- OghamStone_Squirrel
- Place
 - Place
 - Aufbewahrungsort (Repository)
 - Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
 - Kiln region (KilnRegion)
 - ProductionCentre
 - Location (Location)
- Townland
- Townland
- geosparql:Feature

... using the SPARQL endpoint and research tools ...

The screenshot displays the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin interface. The main window is titled "SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin" and contains several panels:

- Query Editor:** Contains a SPARQL query:


```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)
      
```
- GeoConcepts (23):** A list of concepts including AnnotatedThing, Barony, County, Discovery Site, GeographicLocation, Island, Kiln region, Location, OghamSite (highlighted), Place, ProductionCentre, Province, State, Townland, geosparql:Feature, sf:MultiPolygon, sf:Point, sf:Polygon, and wgs84_pos:SpatialThing.
- SPARQL endpoint:** Shows the endpoint URL: `/api/sparql`.
- Results Table:** Displays 196 results with columns: Item, Label, geo, county, and count. The results are sorted by count in descending order.

At the bottom right, there is a URL: <https://t1p.de/v0lg7>.

... analyse it with Open Source Software ...

... and adapt that idea to other datasets!

<https://t1p.de/mdvhn>

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: NFDI4Objects Graph --> ?item ?geo [GeoSPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name: productioncentre

Valid Query

```

1 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
2 PREFIX lado: <http://archaeology.link/ontology#>
3 SELECT ?item ?geo ?kilnregion WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://archaeology.link/ontology#ProductionCentre> .
5 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
6 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
7 ?item lado:clusteredAs ?kr .
8 ?kr rdfs:label ?kilnregion .
9 }
    
```

Filter Concept Results:

GeoConcepts (23)

- AnnotatedThing
- Barony
- County
- Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
- GeographicLocation
- Island
- Kiln region (KilnRegion)
- Location
- Location (Location)
- OghamSite
- Place
- ProductionCentre**
- Province
- State
- Townland
- geosparql:Feature
- sf:MultiPolygon
- sf:Point
- sf:Polygon
- wgs84_pos:SpatialThing

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: English (en)

Show us your Knowledge Graph Ideas!

Hic sunt dracones! Semantics and archaeological Linked Open Data within the FAIRification process and Research Data Lifecycle along the Object Biography

In 2006, Berners-Lee introduced the concept of LOD; in 2018 Sanderson instigated the “Usable” aspect at EuropeanaTech. In 2016, the FAIR principles were introduced: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. Semantic Modelling and Linked Open (Usable) Data are a huge part of Computational Archaeology and also an important part of the FAIRification and Research Data Management (RDM) process inside the Research Data Lifecycle and along the digital object biography.

Our session aims to bring together experts and colleagues interested in learning about FAIR and LOUD data-driven publishing and applications and collecting research application scenarios to jointly promote research domain-specific solutions for research data management. We would like to discuss application-oriented and data-driven investigations into improving technologies for FAIR and LOUD data models as a basis for reproducible and CAREful research and exchange on the Semantic Web. We encourage presenters to derive the problems addressed from real-world datasets and to formulate proposals for solutions, preferably demonstrating (prototypes of) realised data-driven (web-) applications. Due to the thematic relevance, we target a broad and diverse audience, and the challenges described should also be integrated into an archaeological context (excavation, museum, archive, etc.).

Topics

- application of Semantic Web technologies, such as ontologies (e.g. CIDOC-CRM) or RDF, to the archaeological domain
- modelling of archaeological artefacts, the archaeological context, including the specificity of stratigraphy, uncertainty, and vagueness
- development of research tools producing or using FAIR and LOUD data
- identifying sources and dangers of incorrect or ambiguous LOD, e.g., duplicates across different LOD sources
- keeping track of the provenance of data as a means of solving errors and identifying their source
- setting up research-question-based methodologies and tools to label or assess datasets based on their quality
- dealing with ambiguities resulting from multiple links in the LOD cloud
- computer vision or machine learning applications built upon controlled semantic data
- building up Knowledge Graphs by applying semantic and Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies
- modelling comprehensible/reproducible workflows and data flows using RDF for documentation and reproducible research
- use of Linked Open Data related tools in archaeological research, their implementation and/or enhancement
- possibilities, challenges, benefits and risks of the Wikimedia Universe (e.g. Wikidata) in archaeological research
- implementation of reference models such as CIDOC-CRM in real-world datasets and ways to achieve LOD
- graphs of facts, beliefs, and/or assertions as a digital archaeological method
- reasoning with heterogeneous and real-world archaeological data in graphs
- granularity in LOD/graphs/networks
- semantically modelling geospatial data FAIR and LOUD / implementation of GeosPARQL as a geospatial standard in archaeological data

NEW Deadline
24 November 2024

This session is organised by the CAA SIG on Semantics and LOUD in Archaeology (SIG Data-Dragon). The core aim of this SIG is to use the SIG format to raise awareness for Linked Data in archaeology by creating a friendly and open platform to discuss and further develop semantics and LOUD and FAIR data in archaeology.

NFDI4Objects

Community Cluster
Semantic Modelling
& Linked Open Data

Florian Thiery (Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie), **Karsten Tolle** (Goethe University Frankfurt),
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Finis!

Thx :-)

Questions?

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